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there's
something
science
can do.

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[J&J adds novel targeted cell-death drugs to its prostate cancer pipeline:](#) On November 17, Johnson & Johnson acquired Halda Therapeutics for \$3.05 billion, securing its RIPTAC (“regulated induced proximity targeting chimera”) platform. The lead small-molecule drug, HLD-0915, uses this technology to force two proteins inside a cancer cell to bind, triggering selective self-destruction even in treatment-resistant tumors. [Early clinical trial results](#) in patients with advanced prostate cancer suggest great potential.

[US shift away from primate research in biomedical development:](#) On November 21, the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) directed its researchers to end all monkey-based studies by the end of the year, affecting about 200 macaques and several ongoing infectious-disease programs. At the same time, [the US Food and Drug Administration \(FDA\) updated its drug-evaluation requirements](#) to remove primate toxicity studies for certain monoclonal antibody drugs, moving development in the US toward organoids, human-cell systems and computational models.

[Ginkgo Bioworks launches open-source Virtual Cell initiative for AI drug discovery:](#) On November 21, Ginkgo Bioworks introduced the Virtual Cell Pharmacology Initiative (VCPI), an open-source project aimed at creating the world’s largest standardized dataset for AI-based drug discovery. The effort will test more than 100,000 compounds on a single engineered reference cell line and generate about 12 billion gene-expression measurements, giving AI models data to better predict how drugs affect human cells and speed up the search for promising therapeutic candidates.

[UK increases NHS spending on branded medicines to secure an exemption from threatened US tariffs:](#) On December 1, the National Health Service (NHS) agreed to pay pharmaceutical companies up to 25% more for new branded medicines. The change was made in response to US complaints that the UK and other European countries pay much less for medicines, leaving Americans to shoulder a larger share of global drug development costs. After the UK raised its price cap, the US announced an [Agreement in Principle](#) that exempts UK pharmaceuticals from proposed 100% tariffs under Section 232. While this helps the UK avoid major trade penalties, the higher price limit is expected to add about £3 billion to NHS medicine costs, reducing money available for other healthcare services.